

Impact of FRBR on Cataloguing Standards and RDA Implementation

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Abstract

RDA integrates the FRBR conceptual model with cataloguing principles to establish a framework that enhances cataloguers' judgment and improves future systems. FRBR is not a cataloguing code in itself. It illustrates how users can gain advantages from a meticulously organized system centered on the FRBR entities and their interrelations. As an IFLA study, its first impact was on the ISBDs (International Standard Bibliographic Description) in terms of applying recommendations about which data elements should be mandatory and which data elements should be optional.

Methodology: This is a non-empirical study that tries to explore the impact of FRBR on cataloguing standards and RDA implementation.

Findings: The concepts of functional requirements for bibliographic records, resource description and open access were well presented and highlighted. The study also elucidated on the impact of FRBR on cataloguing and RDA implementation.

Conclusion/Recommendations: Since the release of FRBR in 1998, there has been a growing reflection in the bibliographic community around the ideas it represents. FRBR has provided a unifying framework and a common terminology for discussion. Theoretical work on the principles underlying cataloguing had been going on prior to FRBR, but authors had to invent/define their own terms (particularly for entities in FRBR Group 1). The study recommends appropriate training of cataloguers on the current trends in cataloguing practices as well as good maintenance of cataloguing tools and equipment.

Keywords: FRBR (Functional Requirement for Bibliographic Records), RDA, Cataloguing Standards, IFLA Developments, ISBD (International Standard Bibliographic Description)

Introduction

A new edition of AACR was first brought up in the early 2000s. Tom Delsey was chosen as the editor, and work on the new edition (AACR3) began in 2004. The JSC made the decision to thoroughly rewrite AACR2, and the draft part I of AACR3 was made available for consideration in December 2004 (Atinmo, 2013). The JSC decided in April 2005 to completely abandon AACR3 and start over in a completely different way by changing the name of AACR3 to RDA (Resource Description and Access) in response to the feedback on the draft of part I (Bhatt & Mishra, 2012). In order to provide a flexible framework for describing all bibliographic materials, it was agreed that RDA would be based on the conceptual models-Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records (FRBR) and Functional Requirements for Authority Data (FRAD) created by IFLA.

For enterprises that use cutting-edge database technology, FRBR and FRAD give specific attention to digital resources and enable greater efficiency. IFLA's (International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions) guideline known as FRBR (Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records) calls for catalogue databases to be reorganized to better match the conceptual organization of information resources (Bello & Thomson, 2013). It is the foundation on which the new cataloguing code, Resource Description and Access (RDA) is based. An understanding of the FRBR model is essential to the understanding and application of RDA.

Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records (FRBR)

The Resource Description and Access (RDA) Cataloguing Code is the most notable product to date of an ongoing re-conceptualization of cataloguing, and it is the foundation document for FRBR (RDA). It is an effort to create a conceptual framework that may convey a universally accepted notion of what bibliographic records need to contain and what users should expect them to do (Raval & BankLaw, 2013).

The need to fully utilize all of the options for shared cataloguing in the new online environment, as well as a requirement to formulate a reasonable answer to the mounting demands libraries were facing to cut the cost of cataloguing, served as the catalyst for its development. By responding to these economic forces, the authors of FRBR wanted to create an international consensus on how minimal a record could be while still serving its essential purposes (Cabonero & Dolendo, 2013). However, as is sometimes the case, FRBR quickly expanded past the original objectives of those who commissioned it and is today viewed as a full-fledged theory of cataloguing. Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records (FRBR) offers great potential for libraries to develop catalogues that allow users to access bibliographic data in a more effective manner.

The focus on users and their information requirements in FRBR presents excellent opportunity for developing retrieval systems that better assist user information searching (Maxwell, 2012). For online library catalogues, FRBR offers potential solutions to some issues and problems in current catalogues, such as searching for materials with a known author and title, finding works scattered throughout multiple records in current catalogues, collocating at the work and expression level, and reducing the number of redundant searches required for current catalogues by offering effective displays and linking of related records (Bennett et al., 2013). FRBR is a conceptual entity-relationship model developed by the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) that relates user tasks of retrieval and access in online library catalogues and bibliographic databases from a user's perspective.

As links to move across the hierarchy of relationships are provided by the relationships between the entities, it represents a more comprehensive approach to retrieval and access. Due to the fact that the model is distinct from certain cataloguing standards like the Anglo-American Cataloguing Rules (AACR) or the International Standard Bibliographic Description (ISBD), it is considered to be significant. A new conceptual model of the bibliographic universe was introduced in Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records (FRBR), which takes into account the requirements of consumers of bibliographic data (IFLA, 2013).

There are four tasks that information seekers employ when looking for information which have been identified and examined under the FRBR model and they include: Find, Identify, Select and Obtain.

The entity-relationship analysis method, widely used in database design, serves as the foundation for the FRBR model. It is highly theoretical, code-neutral, and independent of systems. Specific relationships bind entities (like people, works, and concepts) together. Relationships and entities are identified and defined by predetermined attributes. There are ten FRBR entities, and these are arranged into three groups. Group 1 entities are "the outcomes of creative or intellectual endeavours.

It is all the resources to which we grant access through our catalogues (Zhang & Salaba, 2019). As explained by Zhang and Salaba, (2019), "Work" denotes a distinct intellectual or artistic creation while "Expression" describes the intellectual or artistic realization of a work. "Manifestation" talks about the physical embodiment of an expression of a work while Item" points to a single example of a manifestation.

Work and expression in the Group 1 entities are abstract concepts, whereas manifestation and item pertain to actual physical objects. A couple of instances of Group 2 entities include Person and Corporate Body. Group 2 entities are "agents who are responsible for the intellectual or artistic content, the physical production and distribution, or the custodianship of any Group 1

company" (Zhang & Salaba, 2019). Group 3 entities that are the subjects of works include: Concept, Object, Event, and Place. Entities from Groups 1 and 2 may also be the subjects of works. The bibliographic movement has been reflecting more and more on the ideas it stands for since the release of FRBR in 1998.

FRBR has provided the discussion with a unifying framework and a common language. Theoretical work on cataloguing principles had been in existence before FRBR, but authors had to develop/define their own nomenclature (particularly for entities in FRBR Group 1). Due to the fact that there was no standardized language, the word "work" may indicate different things depending on who was using it. Since the inception of FRBR, most theoretical research and applications have used FRBR-specific nomenclature, making it simpler for one study to build upon another (Zhang, & Athena, 2019). FRBR is limited to bibliographic records.

For cataloguing librarians, expanding the modeling to include the entities, attributes, and relationships found in authority data was the initial and most natural desire. Glenn Patton served as the chairman of the Functional Requirements and Numbering of Authority Records (FRANAR) which began in 1999.

The resulting model, answering to the first aspect of their task, is dubbed Functional Requirements of Authority Data (FRAD) and is still undergoing world-wide evaluation (Joint Steering Committee for Revision of AACR, and American Library Association, 2012). The Functional Requirements of Authority Records (FRAR) acronym was used for the model's initial release in July 2005, but after receiving feedback that made it clear that the model's focus is authority data rather than the entire authority record, the name was changed.

The emphasis is on the authority data required to support catalogues that use the idea of authority work. The entity family was missing from Group 2 in FRBR, as noted by work done in the archive community that FRANAR was particularly aware of (Khan, 2016). The FRBR is meant to be a living model that is updated and maintained, not a static document. The development of the FRAD and FRSAR models will maintain FRBR's compatibility with them.

The FRBR Review Group, which was founded in 2002 as a working group and changed into a review group in 2003, is in charge of maintaining the FRBR model, producing guidelines and interpretive documents, disseminating the model, and maintaining relationships with other related organizations. The notion of the expression entity that gave rise to the initial amendment proposal to the FRBR text of 1998 is currently being clarified by the Working Group on the Expression Entity (Nwalo, 2013).

Another significant area is the role of the Working Group on Aggregates to continue investigating modeling of aggregations of all kinds. Examples include serials, anthologies of

stories or essays, and other whole/part arrangements. A working group of the FRBR Review Group has been meeting with the ICOM-CIDOC CRM group for a number of years in order to reconcile FRBR with the Conceptual Reference Model (CRM).

The objective is to formalize FRBR in an object-oriented manner and to add concepts to the model that are drawn from descriptions of museum artifacts, especially the case of single-item manifestations. CRM is event-based, and this viewpoint will be useful for FRBR's future development (Nwalo, 2013). The FRBR approach is a novel way of explaining the relationships between books, writers, and subjects. The mechanics of how it works are novel, even if it can only be done using computers, but the principles it uses are old. The fundamental rules of cataloguing and librarianship are embodied in it. This essay will examine some of those laws, how FRBR operates and complies with them, and some current initiatives to improve existing catalogues with FRBR.

There is not a single material object that can be recognized as a work; it is an abstract concept. Although several realizations or representations of the work aid in its recognition, the work itself only exists in the common elements of these various incarnations. IFLA uses italics to highlight entity names. Work comes first in a hierarchy. It is followed by "expression," which is defined as "the conceptual realization of a work in the shape of [alpha-numeric], [musical], or [choreographic] notation, sound, image, object, movement, etc., or in any combination of such forms" (IFLA 18). Expressions are abstract in and of themselves.

The specific intellectual or aesthetic form that a work adopts each time it is "realized" is described as an expression. Expression includes things like the precise notes, phrasing, etc. that come from the realization of a musical work as well as the individual words, phrases, paragraphs, etc. that come from the realization of a work in the form of a text (Jans, & Sheikh, 2011).

Third in the hierarchy is manifestation, which is concrete. A manifestation is described in the dictionary as "a work's expression as a tangible manifestation. Manuscripts, books, magazines, maps, posters, sound recordings, movies, videos, CD-ROMs, multimedia kits, etc. (Khan, 2016) are all included in the definition of "manifestation," along with many other types of materials. In terms of both intellectual content and physical form, manifestation serves as an entity for all physical objects with the same traits (IFLA 20).

The fourth and topmost stratum of the hierarchy, represented by the thing known as "a solitary instance of a manifestation," is graspable (IFLA 23). The term "item" refers to each copy of a book that manifests as a physical object. Each copy of Yo-Yo Ma's freshly released CD of cello suites is an item in the music industry. Items may differ from one another "where those changes are the result of events external to the intent of the maker of the manifestation" (for example,

damage sustained after the manufacture of the item, binding completed by a library, etc.) (Jans, & Sheikh, 2011).

Resource Description and Access (RDA)

Resource Description and Access (RDA), a substitute for past cataloguing projects in the electronic world, has been in use since the middle of 2010 (Atinmo, 2011). The ideas of Anglo-American Cataloguing Laws are built upon by RDA (AACR). The Joint Steering Committee for RDA Development (JSC) concurred that AACR2 would not assist Rogers users in the 1990s as we move into the twenty-first century (Josh, 2013). It was structured before the internet around card catalogues, linear citation displays, and computer-usable metadata.

The JSC regularly heard complaints about AACR2 in the 1990s, especially its shortfalls that did not accommodate electronic resources and this is the motivating factor RDA growth.

The conceptual framework outlined in the Functional Specifications for Authority Data (FRAD) model (Bello & Mansurur, 2011) is included in the Practical Requirement for Bibliographic Information (FRBR) (RDA model, 2011). By focusing on the content and carriers and interpreting their linked people, families, and corporate bodies in terms of their distinctive traits, these conceptual models have offered a fresh viewpoint on how resources are described. For the international group of respondents, the FRBR organizations and relationships and the terms used to describe them were relevant.

The use of identifying features in the resource specification to fulfill simple user tasks was one of the main aspects of the conceptual models: to find, describe, select and receive (IFLA 2013). FRBR offers a structure to address user tasks, and FRBR entities and elements translate into RDA as the data elements for bibliographic description and access, and the relationships among entities. RDA combines the FRBR conceptual model with cataloguing principles to provide the foundations to build cataloguer judgment and better systems for the future. FRBR is not itself a cataloguing code. But it demonstrates how users can benefit from a well-structured system designed around the FRBR entities and relationships.

Impact of FRBR on Cataloguing and RDA Implementation

How will FRBR affect cataloguing? First, integrated library system (ILS) vendors will need to develop catalogues that implement and manage the FRBR model. Once developed, cataloguers will describe a *work* and its *expressions* only once, thus making their work more efficient and less time consuming. “Current practice, which is based on cataloguing manifestations, requires the repetition of work and expression information every time a new manifestation is described”

(Zhang & Salaba, 2019). FRBR can help increase creation and utilization of uniform title authority records which would lead to easier identification of works and expressions.

RDA (Resource Description and Access) cataloguing standards are based on FRBR, and future implementation of both will promote uniform metadata creation that will hopefully “facilitate interoperability and, therefore, will allow bibliographic information to be shared not only among all libraries in the world but also between all information agencies, such as museums, digital libraries, and archives (Zhang & Salaba, 2019). FRBR offers a structure to address user tasks, and FRBR entities and elements translate into RDA as the data elements for bibliographic description and access, and the relationships among entities.

RDA combines the FRBR conceptual model with cataloguing principles to provide the foundations to build cataloger judgment and better systems for the future. FRBR is not itself a cataloguing code. It demonstrates how users can benefit from a well-structured system designed around the FRBR entities and relationships. FRBR perfectly embodies the long-standing fundamental objectives of a catalogue and a library service. It goes beyond merely listing details of a particular copy or edition of a book (or other bibliographic entity), instead using a work-expression-manifestation-item hierarchy of entities and relationships. The creators of these entities, and their subjects, are also entities, and also related, making a rich, informative web of information and knowledge that can be searched or browsed.

Conclusion

Since the release of FRBR in 1998, there has been a growing reflection in the bibliographic community around the ideas it represents. FRBR has provided a unifying framework and a common terminology for discussion. Theoretical work on the principles underlying cataloguing had been going on prior to FRBR, but authors had to invent/define their own terms (particularly for entities in FRBR Group 1). No system of terms had entered into common use, and, for example, the word work had different meanings depending on who was using it. Since the inception of FRBR, most theoretical studies and applications have been using FRBR terminology, and this makes it easier for one study to build on another.

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